

Energy Citizenship and Energy Communities for a Clean-Energy Transition

A Horizon2020 Project

The EU's ambitious decarbonisation targets cannot be met by technology alone. What are the social, economic and legal conditions that will enable a shift in our energy model: from a centralised energy regime to a decentralised one, from a society of passive energy consumers to one of empowered, engaged energy citizens?

Gathering insights from the fields of law, economics and psychology, EC² will provide answers on how to facilitate and strengthen energy citizenship. Knowledge co-creation with municipalities, energy communities and citizens will enhance the research to deliver recommendations that support the EU's energy and decarbonisation goals.

The project will develop a clear conceptualisation of energy citizenship, and gather actionable insights into the optimal conditions for it to flourish. It places a special focus on the role of energy communities and how their set-up can help - or hinder - the creation of energy citizens.

The insights gained will lead to policies, tools and practices that will support the sustainable, just, inclusive transition to a low-carbon society with citizens at the centre.

Project Partners

- ZSI Centre for Social Innovation, AT
- Universität Graz, AT
- Universität Leipzig, DE
- Uniwersytet Ekonomiczny we Wrocławiu, PL
- Rijksuniversiteit Groningen, NL
- ICLEI European Secretariat GmbH, DE
- Global Ecovillage Network of Europe E.V., DE
- Spółdzielnia Mieszkaniowa Wrocław-Południe, PL
- Gmina Prusice, PL
- Comune di Scalenghe, IT
- Ture Nirvane Societa' Cooperativa Sociale di Comunita', IT
- Arterra Bizimodu, ES
- Buurkracht Projecten B.V., NL
- Groningen municipality, NL

EC² Objectives

Through empirical research, theoretical analysis and co-creation activities with diverse stakeholders the project will...

- ✓ Provide **evidence-based tools and a digital training program** to scale-up energy citizenship and energy communities
- ✓ Develop **actionable policy recommendations and briefs for policymakers** by connecting project findings to policy and practice
- ✓ Supply **tested tools to support energy citizenship and energy communities**
- ✓ Foster **inclusivity of energy citizenship** and energy communities
- ✓ **Deepen our understanding of energy citizenship** and how to empower citizens to become energy citizens
- ✓ Identify **legal and economic conditions supporting or hindering energy citizenship**
- ✓ Understand how energy citizenship shapes and influences the energy sector, the energy transition, and the achievement of EU decarbonisation goals.

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Advancing research, policy and practice

To advance the state of the art in the area of study and to inform policy and practice on energy communities and energy citizenship for a low-carbon transition, the project will deliver:

1 A catalogue of **legal and economic barriers and facilitators** of energy citizenship

2 A scale to measure **how energy citizenship emerges in individuals**

3 **Co-created tools** for energy communities

4 Energy citizenship **policy briefings, citizen empowerment kits, and an energy citizenship academy**

The EC² Methodology

EC² employs both an **interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary approach** to gain an in-depth conceptualisation of energy citizenship. It will also enhance the understanding of the barriers and facilitators of energy communities and energy citizenship, and the interplay between the two. EC² works with:

- ✓ **Theoretical research** on legal, economic and psychological aspects of energy communities and citizenship
- ✓ **Empirical lab and field studies** on energy communities and energy citizenship
- ✓ **Co-creation workshops** with key stakeholders including municipalities, energy communities and citizens

● Municipality ● Energy community ● Community network

In-depth Country Studies

The project's outputs will be informed by research including **in-depth studies** in four countries: **Netherlands, Spain, Italy and Poland**. These will integrate the expertise of in-country research partners with the on-the-ground experiences of local energy communities and municipalities in diverse cultural and socio-economic settings. This diversity of actors and level of advancement will allow a better understanding of barriers and drivers of energy citizenship development.

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